

Lowest minima for the Thomson problem on the unit disk: supplementary material

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Abstract

This document contains supplemental material of the paper [1], where the Thomson problem in the disk has been studied. Here we report the lowest minima for all the configuration with $N \leq 330$ and selected configurations for larger N . To the best of our knowledge configurations with $N > 5000$ had never before been considered in the literature.

1 Records for $10 \leq N \leq 330$

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 $E = 739.342746993$

$N = 38$ $N_B = 28$
 $E = 804.920002725$

$N = 39$ $N_B = 29$
 $E = 851.911303255$

$N = 40$ $N_B = 29$
 $E = 900.118715332$

$N = 41$ $N_B = 30$
 $E = 949.851580407$

$N = 42$ $N_B = 30$
 $E = 1000.82540195$

$N = 43$ $N_B = 31$
 $E = 1053.30445176$

$N = 44$ $N_B = 31$
 $E = 1107.07938120$

$N = 45$ $N_B = 32$
 $E = 1162.33037735$

$N = 46$ $N_B = 32$
 $E = 1218.98082510$

$N = 47$ $N_B = 33$
 $E = 1277.00698195$

$N = 48$ $N_B = 33$
 $E = 1336.37522344$

$N = 49$ $N_B = 34$
 $E = 1397.20092800$

$N = 50$ $N_B = 34$
 $E = 1459.58211946$

$N = 51$ $N_B = 35$
 $E = 1523.20919609$

$N = 52$ $N_B = 35$
 $E = 1588.20649120$

$N = 53$ $N_B = 36$
 $E = 1654.63776147$

$N = 54$ $N_B = 36$
 $E = 1722.68422695$

$N = 55$ $N_B = 37$
 $E = 1791.9736857$

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$N = 285$ $N_B = 117$
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$N = 286$ $N_B = 118$
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$N = 330$ $N_B = 130$
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2 Selected configurations

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 $E = 736977.577929$

$N = 2000$ $N_B = 442$
 $E = 3003830.44969$

$N = 5000$ $N_B = 820$

$E = 19087485.4425$

$N = 10000$ $N_B = 1307$
 $E = 76987197.7343$

$$N = 14180 \quad N_B = 1647$$
$$E = 155297471.174$$

$$N = 40886 \quad N_B = 3356$$

$$E = 1300043776.14$$

Figure 111: Details of the border of the configuration with 40886 charges.

References

- [1] P. Amore and U. Zarate, "Thomson problem in the disk" (2023)

Figure 112: Details of the border of the configuration with 40886 charges.

Figure 113: Details of the configuration with 40886 charges.

Figure 114: Details of the configuration with 40886 charges.